

Detection of temporal changes of the Omega House at the Athenian Agora

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the role of 3D visualization and analysis of monuments and archaeological sites in producing useful data regarding their preservation condition. The progress made in 3D digitization technologies, in combination with finding new data processing algorithms, have enabled reliable and highly detailed digitization of the characteristics of different parts of the monuments. Due to both the effects of nature and human intervention, monuments and sites all over the world have changed over time. The use of analog documentation data can help significantly towards this direction. In this work, we use as case study a luxurious residential complex in the Athenian Agora, known as Omega house. We use a retrospective 3D model, created with photographs taken in the late 60's and early 70's, in comparison with a 3D model made with contemporary digital photos, taken in 2017. All models are georeferenced. The old model is produced using analog terrestrial photographs and aerial photos taken by a blimp. The new one is created by terrestrial digital photographs in combination with images taken by unmanned aerial vehicle commonly known as a drone. The 3D models have been divided into smaller parts so that we can analyze them with greater accuracy separately, and then the whole models were compared between them too. The Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) modeling scheme is used and Boolean operations are applied to find the difference and intersection of the models. The comparison that is carried out in the current work elaborates on legacy data usefulness and utility for monitoring the Omega House condition. The type of investigation proposed in this work proves that legacy data can be repurposed and attain a new role through change detection techniques.

Keywords: Omega house, 3D model, legacy data, archaeology, temporal change detection, Constructive Solid Geometry

45 Archaeological sites and heritage buildings globally face different and continuous challenges with
46 regard to vulnerability. Natural threat events, erosion, vegetation and human intervention like excavation
47 devoid of preservation, pollution and unlimited urbanization bring about presentation and preservation
48 problems (Fatorić & Seekamp, 2017; Hamilton et al., 2009; Lemos, 2007). There is an everyday need for
49 preventative measures towards monuments' preservation. Condition monitoring and temporal change
50 detection of the monuments can be carried out by means of multifaceted approaches from the literature
51 (Abate, 2018; Moropoulou et al., 2013; Wallace et al., 2017). In the past two decades, photogrammetric
52 3D modeling of archaeological sites has become ordinary whilst methods of extracting data from archival
53 materials to create 3D models have been developed (Falkingham, 2014; Discamps et al., 2016; Peppas
54 et al., 2018; Wallace, 2017). Retrospective photogrammetry permits to take a new look at the past condition
55 of archaeological sites as in the time of first excavation. The current paper treats the issue of using
56 retrospective models in comparison to contemporary models for assessing deterioration relative to time,
57 preservation, and natural processes.

58 Two 3D models of the site called Omega house, a luxurious residential complex of the Roman period in
59 the Athenian Agora, serve for case study (Camp 1989; Camp 2010). The retrospective model is as it was
60 when excavated in 1972, and the contemporary is of the site after 45 years in 2017 (Wallace et al., 2017;
61 Wallace, 2017). Omega house was selected for the retrospective aspect of this project due to the
62 scrupulousness of documentation during its excavation.

63 In this paper, we compare the two models utilizing Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) operations
64 (Bernstein & Fussler, 2009; Campen & Kobbelt, 2010; Chen et al., 2021; De Araiijo et al., 2015; Nehring-
65 Winkel, 2021; Trettner & Kobbelt, 2021) for performing Boolean operations on the Omega house models.
66 Also, distance and volume calculations are carried out. The 3D photogrammetric models of the site dated
67 in 1972 and 2017 enable the examination and measurement of the site's aspects. This work is organized
68 into four sections. The Methodology is presented in the second section and the Results are given in the
69 third section. Conclusions are drawn in the last section.

Scope and Methodology

72 The principal aim of this paper is to check the accuracy of the retrospective (1972) model, by comparing
73 it with the contemporary one (2017) of measured accuracy $\pm 1\text{cm}$ and to assess how much the site has
74 changed between the time of its first excavation in 1972 and its current state.

75 The initial version of the retrospective model 1972 and of the contemporary model 2017 have been
76 obtained from the source (Wallace et al., 2017; Wallace, 2017). Both models 1972 and 2017 are
77 georeferenced. With regard to the relative accuracy of the retrospective model compared to the
78 contemporary model, the RMSE equals 0.339m, 0.344m and 1.795m for the easting, northing and elevation
79 residuals of model 1972 from model 2017, respectively (Panagiotopoulou et al., 2023). Processing of the
80 3D photogrammetric models has been performed by means of the 3D point cloud processing software
81 named CloudCompare (CloudCompare, 2022), on the purpose of detecting temporal changes.

82 In the present work, CSG is applied on the Omega house models (Chen et al., 2021; CloudCompare,
83 2022; De Araiijo et al., 2015; Nehring-Winkel, 2021; Trettner & Kobbelt, 2021) to calculate the Boolean
84 operations that are called difference and intersection. The Boolean operation of difference can disclose
85 whether and to what degree the contemporary model has been altered in comparison with the
86 retrospective model. The Boolean operation of intersection can provide the common portion of the two
87 models; thus, it can reveal the monument parts that have not changed throughout the time of 45 years.
88 Regarding the calculation of the distances between the two models for 1972 and 2017, the distance
89 computation algorithm called Iterative Closest Point (ICP) is applied, and the octree and Cloud-to-Mesh
90 (C2M) distances are utilized (Cignoni et al., 1998; Girardeau-Montaut et al., 2005). As far as the distance
91 calculations are concerned, they can indicate variations in the terrain during the time of intercomparison.
92 Additionally, the volume calculations could disclose the occurrence of material decay.

93 The current work is a continuation of the already published paper (Panagiotopoulou et al., 2023). The
94 motivation for new experiments lies on the map with the overlap of available photographs in the 1972
95 archival data, Figure 1, which indicates that the central south portions of the modeling represent the least
96 disparity between old (1972) and new (2017) models. The central south portions of Omega house between
97 the old and new models are under new investigation in the present work. The east and northeast parts
98 have the least overlap in historical photographs and result in a greater disparity in measurements between
99 the two sets of models. The central south portions of Omega house which have been selected for
100 investigation in the current study are demonstrated in Figure 2.

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Results

103 The selected parts of the monument along with the calculated C2M signed distances in cm, where the
104 model 2017 has been considered as reference, are depicted in Figures 3-9. The Boolean operations
105 Difference 1972-2017 and Intersection $1972 \cap 2017$ can also be found in the corresponding part figures
106 where calculation was feasible. Volume and surface calculations are depicted in Figures 10-13.

107 The values of the minimum and maximum C2M distances that have been calculated for the seven
108 selected parts of Omega House are given in Table 1. The parts 2 and 6 present the greatest distances
109 ranging from 0.630 to -1.324 cm and from 1.040 to -0.895 cm, respectively. The parts 3, 4 and 7 give the
110 smaller distance differences. In specific, for part 7 the distances range from 0.611 to -0.825 cm, for part 4
111 the distances extend from 0.772 to -0.732 cm while for part 3 the distance range covers from 0.892 to -
112 0.681 cm. As far as the monument parts 1 and 5 are concerned, these demonstrate the intermediate
113 distance ranges of 1.782 and 1.759 cm, correspondingly.

114 The values of the volume and surface calculations are presented in Table 2. Part 1 in the model 2017
115 appears with increased volume per 42.60 % in relation to the model 1972. Parts 2 and 3 in the model 2017
116 also present increased volume per 12.24 and 5.89 %, respectively, in comparison with the model 1972.
117 With regard to the parts 4, 5, 6 and 7, these appear to have decreased in volume in 2017 in relation to the
118 model 1972. In detail, parts 5 and 6 have decreased in volume per 26.87 and 28.55 %, correspondingly.
119 Parts 4 and 7 have slightly decreased volume in 2017 per 2.03 and 2.98 % accordingly when compared with
120 the 1972 model. As far as the surface calculations are concerned, these indicate that the model parts 2, 3,
121 4 and 7 have the same surface in both models 1972 and 2017. However, the 2017 model parts 5 and 6
122 present increased surface per 20 % in relation to the model 1972. Regarding the part 1, it appears with
123 reduced surface per 11.11 % in 2017 in comparison with 1972.

124 This comparison can contribute to the evaluation of what sort of deterioration occurs by natural
125 processes over 45 years. From an archaeological point of view, the observed transformations could be due
126 to material decay, debris and terrain variations during the time of intercomparison, and additionally, during
127 the annual cleaning of the site of dirt or debris that may have been removed. Some walls show significant
128 loss of material.

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Figure 1 –Map of camera overlap in 1972 modeling (Panagiotopoulou et al., 2023).

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Figure 2 –Selection of Omega House parts (1-7).

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Figure 3 –a) Selected part 1 of Omega House (see Figure 1 for part selection) b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017.

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Figure 4 –a) Selected part 2 of Omega House b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017.

1972 Model

2017 Model

2.5 m

a)

2.5 m

b)

c)

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Figure 5 –a) Selected part 3 of Omega House b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017 c) The Boolean operations on the models Difference 1972-2017 and Intersection 1972∩2017 .

1972 Model

2017 Model

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a)

2 m

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Figure 6 –a) Selected part 4 of Omega House b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017 c) The Boolean operations on the models Difference 1972-2017 and Intersection 1972 \cap 2017 .

1972 Model

2017 Model

1.5 m

a)

1.5 m

b)

Difference 1972-2017

Intersection 1972∩2017

1.5 m

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Figure 7 –a) Selected part 5 of Omega House b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017 c) The Boolean operations on the models Difference 1972-2017 and Intersection 1972∩2017 .

1972 Model

2017 Model

1.5 m

a)

1.5 m

b)

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Figure 8 –a) Selected part 6 of Omega House b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017.

1972 Model

2017 Model

1 m

a)

1 m

b)

c)

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Figure 9 –a) Selected part 7 of Omega House b) C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017 c) The Boolean operations on the models Difference 1972-2017 and Intersection 1972∩2017 .

a) Part 1, 1972

b) Part 1, 2017

c) Part 2, 1972

d) Part 2, 2017

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Figure 10—Volume (m³) and surface (m²) calculation for the selected a) 1972 Part 1 b) 2017 Part 1 c) 1972 Part 2 d) 2017 Part 2 of Omega House.

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a) Part 3, 1972

b) Part 3, 2017

c) Part 4, 1972

d) Part 4, 2017

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Figure 11 –Volume (m³) and surface (m²) calculation for the selected a) 1972 Part 3 b) 2017 Part 3 c) 1972 Part 4 d) 2017 Part 4 of Omega House.

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a) Part 5, 1972

b) Part 5, 2017

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a) Part 7, 1972

b) Part 7, 2017

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Figure 13 –Volume (m³) and surface (m²) calculation for the selected a) 1972 Part 7 b) 2017 Part 7.

Table 1 – C2M signed distances in cm with reference the model 2017. The maximum and minimum values are given regarding each one of the seven selected parts of Omega House.

Omega House Part	Minimum Distance (cm)	Maximum Distance (cm)
Part 1	-1.006	0.776
Part 2	-1.324	0.630
Part 3	-0.681	0.892
Part 4	-0.732	0.772
Part 5	-0.713	1.046
Part 6	-0.895	1.040
Part 7	-0.825	0.611

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Table 2 –Volume and surface calculation values for the 1972 and 2017 models, regarding the seven selected parts of Omega House in Figures 9-12.

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Omega House Part	Volume (m ³) 1972	Volume (m ³) 2017	Surface (m ²) 1972	Surface (m ²) 2017
Part 1	25.492	14.635	18	16
Part 2	61.272	53.767	20	20
Part 3	76.055	71.574	18	18
Part 4	43.901	44.786	12	12
Part 5	41.898	53.164	10	12
Part 6	47.115	60.565	10	12
Part 7	38.196	39.341	8	8

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Conclusions

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In this work the map of camera overlap in 1972 modeling has given the motivation for further exploring the central south portions of Omega House. Seven parts of the monument have been selected in the particular area to perform comparisons between the 1972 and 2017 models. There, C2M distances between the models 1972 and 2017 lie from -1.324 to 1.046 cm, with reference the model 2017. Volume comparisons of the central south portions reveal partly reduction per 42.60 % as well as partly increase per 28.55 % in the 2017 model in relation to the 1972 model. Furthermore, the surface calculations denote preservation between the 1972 and 2017 models in five out of the seven selected parts.

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The retrospective model, based entirely on archival material, has been proven to be quite efficient since the maximum differences between the two models lie between -1.3 to 1 cm.

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Moreover, the state of the Omega House is in a good condition overall, although it has been exposed to the elements of nature for more than 50 years.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

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The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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